

**REVISUALIZING SAARC: THE ROLE OF PUBLIC
DIPLOMACY IN INDIA'S CULTURE BASED FOREIGN POLICY
– A REALIST PARADIGM**

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Abstract

A war of ideas and perceptions dominates the contemporary geopolitical landscape. As an aspiring global leader advocating for an alternate global order, India cannot allow itself to be presented on a weak regional footing. The paper explores if SAARC could be to India, what NATO is to America or SCO is to China [the nature and purpose of organizations may vary, but the focus here is on regional leadership]. India needs to strategically revisualize the SAARC grouping where it has leadership potential to harness its global ambitions while ensuring national security. The strategy of Public Diplomacy in capturing the imagination of the people of the SAARC countries to win good will and trust through cultural initiatives, university exchange programs, trade, development initiatives, people-to-people contact and most importantly strategic communication through different mediums will go a long way in building India's image. And, since, public diplomacy is about influencing governments through their public, it will also help make bilateral engagements less susceptible to change in governments in the neighborhood. The paper argues the restrengthening of efforts in alternate diplomacy engaging beyond state and government institutions. It proposes the need for a robust public diplomacy strategy which is specifically structured around India's objectives in its engagement with SAARC.

The paper also aims to examine if policy makers can revisit the Gujral Doctrine and build upon it? And how it can be integrated with Public

Diplomacy to strengthen India's Culture based Foreign Policy? The paper identifies the importance of 'network model' over the 'club model' of diplomacy in engaging with a proliferated list of non-state actors in forwarding the objectives of Public Diplomacy. It submits that Leadership flows from assuming responsibility, bearing patience and in capacity building to offer a good bargain. India needs to broaden its vision in regional engagement and help its neighbors come out of the 'Small State Syndrome'. It should emphatically convey that its public diplomacy is aimed at building mutual trust, interdependence and collective growth to further achieve global peace and security, and is not a means of propaganda. While it needs to alienate its engagement with the SAARC countries from the China prism, it also needs to be fully aware of the building geopolitical dynamics in its trans region for example the Tehran-Beijing-Moscow axis and its larger ramifications. Since the paper is premised on strategizing soft power for national interest, it argues that the various initiatives should be coupled with gradually revitalizing the stalled activities that were undertaken or proposed under the SAARC platform like the SAARC Development Fund, before working on the larger trans regional collaborations like the Turkmenistan-Afghanistan-Pakistan-India and Iran-Pakistan-India pipelines. It bases the above argument on the submission that domestic policy should not overwhelm foreign policy.

Keywords: SAARC, Public Diplomacy, Foreign Policy, National Interest, Global Leadership, Realism

Introduction

The famous Brazilian journalist Pepe Escobar writing for the Cradle Media in February 2024 stated that “World War III is here” (Escobar, 2024). As unrealistic as it may sound, the world today does stand in a state of war of conflicting ideas, perceptions and a realignment of alliances, backed by assertive propaganda, and overt or covert hard power influence. In the midst of this, as the Rule Based International Order (RBIO) slides fatally, there is a remarkable rise of emerging economies challenging the status quo and advocating for an alternate global order based on democratic principles and multipolarity (Latham, 2022; “The BRICS Summit 2023: Seeking an Alternate World Order?” n.d.). India, too, as an aspiring global leader is recalibrating its global engagement, while it continues to face challenges in the neighborhood (Chinoy, 2023).

Therefore, the primary question before this paper is, ‘with all its global ambitions can India allow itself to be presented on a weak regional footing?’. In engaging with this question, the paper explores if SAARC could be to India, what NATO is to America or SCO is to China [the nature and purpose of organizations may vary, but the focus here is on regional leadership]. The paper argues the need for India to strategically revisualize the SAARC grouping where it has leadership potential, and in doing so it evaluates the role of Public Diplomacy in winning people’s good will in the region and in building its leadership image. The attempt is to assess the possibility of viewing SAARC beyond the securitization prism to a leveraging point in geopolitics. International Relations and Diplomacy has a lot to do with a state’s global outlook, and how it is perceived globally. This paper is both an attempt to reorient our analysis of the SAARC grouping, and to further improve India’s global perception on its leadership credibility.

Theoretical Framework

The paper incorporates an unstructured theory of Public Diplomacy in making a prospective study of India’s engagement with the SAARC so as to optimize its regional diplomacy.

Figure 1: Prepared by the Researcher

Public Diplomacy is a way of Soft Power Diplomacy where state’s strategy is to directly communicate and influence the opinion of the people

of another country through different mediums ranging from trade to cultural exchanges and branding through media communication (“What Is PD?” 2023). It is an alternate form of diplomacy that goes beyond state-to-state interaction to encompass the role of multiple actors based on the ‘network model’ as against the ‘club model’ of diplomacy (Heine, 2006). It is a form of open diplomacy through public lobbying which critically focuses on Foreign Public Relations (PR) exercise (Mamchii, 2023).

Further, the paper uses the Public Diplomacy theory with a realist approach as against the traditional understanding of Soft Power being a neo-liberal paradigm. It views the alternate model of diplomacy through power dynamics to put India in a position of leverage vis-à-vis its regional and global geopolitics. The paper also draws on the theory of leadership in International Relations to evaluate the role of ‘influence’ in making a state a “great power” (Triyaningsih & Kantun, 2018).

In its structure the paper follows a rational, comparative and an analytical method of study (Glaser, 2010).

SAARC in India's Global Ambitions

Over the last decade India has enhanced its active participation in and with existing groupings like QUAD, BIMSTEC, ASEAN, BRICS and also formed newer partnerships like I2U2 (Kakkar, 2023). However, for India's global ambitions to materialize it is important that it work on its regional integration, in neglecting which it will allow its competing power to fill the gap, something that has already been in full swing. SAARC's importance in India's global ambitions can be understood as a fine inter-play of geoeconomics, geostrategy and geopolitics.

Geoeconomic Significance:

In 2005, India and China had the same trade volume with the South Asian region (2023). However, over the years, while India's trade with the region has remained less than 4%, China's trade with South Asia has jumped from \$100 billion in 2013 to \$197.4 billion in 2022, witnessing an average annual growth rate of 8.3% (Sinha & Sareen, 2020; n.d). Not only outside its region, China is also simultaneously expanding economic cooperation in East Asia (or Asia-Pacific region). It is a part of the Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement (RCEP) and actively

applying to join the Comprehensive and Progressive Agreement for Trans-Pacific Partnership (CPTPP) (Wei, Gao, & Elahi, 2022). This data becomes critical because in International Relations geo-politics and geo-economics are a mutually interdependent and driving force. For India's geo-political rise, the nature and stature of its regional geo-economics will play an impacting role.

Geostrategic Significance:

Along with the geo-economic factor, SAARC is also geo-strategically important for India. With the docking of the Chinese spy ships or 'research' vessels in Maldives, after the Indian troops were ordered to leave by the island nation, China completes its 'string of pearls' with its already existing naval bases in Hambantota (Srilanka), Karachi (Pakistan), and Doraleh (Djibouti) (Som & Srinivasan, 2024). For India, that aspires to be a net-security provider in the Indo-Pacific this is not an encouraging development, especially as the Chinese President orders its armed forces to 'coordinate preparation for military conflicts at sea' (Business Standard, 2024).

Geopolitical Significance:

In today's complex geopolitical landscape, Foreign Policies cannot be made in isolation. Decisions made by a state in one region have far reaching impact. Therefore, India's engagement with SAARC cannot be a stand-alone issue centered around its animosity with Pakistan. Increasing influence in multilateral forums is crucial for a state to be a "great power". Further, one forum cannot take away from the other its importance. BIMSTEC cannot be considered as an alternative to SAARC for reasons including the history and nature of the groupings, the differing geopolitical significance, and also that, while SAARC is a wholly South Asian organization, BIMSTEC on the other hand is an inter-regional organization. In fact, BIMSTEC's own charter describes it as a bridge between SAARC and ASEAN (Bhattacharjee, 2023).

Significance of SAARC in Global Geopolitical Realignment

As the Global geo-political realities change, the world is undergoing significant realignment with the formation of new alliances, partnerships and groupings. Over India's head is the formation of the Tehran-Beijing-

Moscow Axis (Ludtke, 2023) and till before the political upheaval in Pakistan, by-passing it was a budding alliance, the Turkey-Iran-Pakistan-Malaysia bloc (Rafiq, 2021). While the future of this bloc remains uncertain because of the political changes in Pakistan, its potential will always remain alive. Further, reports suggest Chinese military analyst suggest supporting the formation of a new alliance with Pakistan, Iran and Turkey, something that Iran has already proposed (Mazhari, 2021; Sajid, 2020). From this perspective reviving SAARC becomes strategically important for India.

Figure 2: TAPI and IPI; Source: Comparison of IPI and TAPI Gas Pipelines (Elahi, 2016)

Further, normalizations in the region especially with Pakistan is essential for accelerating the other inter-regional initiatives like the Turkmenistan-Afghanistan-Pakistan-India (TAPI) and Iran-Pakistan-India (IPI) gas pipelines (ANI, 2023; Sahay & Roshandel, 2010).

Reconfiguring the Gujral Doctrine – A Way to Cultural Realism

In the last decade India has evolved from being non-aligned to multi-aligned, and its foreign policy has become more pragmatic (Raghav, 2017). It has moved out of its Panipat mentality and is controlling global narrative (Khzmalyan, 2020). But the one area where significant work still needs to be done is in building a 'strategic culture' or 'cultural realism', where cultural values are incorporated in realpolitik. Dr. S. Jaishankar, the

External Affairs Minister of India, in his book 'The India Way', described the contemporary world order as a 'Bazaar Model' where everything is transactional (Jaishankar, 2020). While it is an acute analytical submission, this paper takes it forward in arguing that, 'in foreign policy, all transactions are not necessarily proportional', especially when it comes to neighborhood; and here comes in the importance of Gujral Doctrine, that primarily stresses on 'not asking for reciprocity with its neighbors, but to give and accommodate what it can in good faith and trust' along with other fundamental principles of mutual engagement (Murthy, 1999). While this doctrine might not have been entirely successful, we can still draw upon its essence to build India's 'strategic culture' with a long-term perspective. A case in reference here can be China's foreign policy an important element of which is its 'strategic deception' where 'it targets an opponent's strategic assessment process about foreign capabilities and intentions' (Anderson & Engstrom, 2009). For example, while China vehemently challenges United States militarily in the Indo-Pacific, the two powers share great economic ties to the extent that China has heavily invested in Sovereign bonds in the United States and is its second largest trading partner (Hirsch, 2022; Statista Research Department, 2024; Zhang & Zhang, 2023). Another interesting juxtapose principle of China's foreign policy is its emphasis on 'Confucianism', under which it does not interfere with the internal politics of regime establishment or change in a foreign country, something that India has been accused of meddling in Bangladesh, Nepal and Maldives (Jonghyuk, 2023; Times, 2024; Welle, 2024). China has strategic interests in Pakistan but it strictly refrained from interfering in the ongoing political upheaval in the country despite the fact that in Imran Khan China and Pakistan saw mutual interest, bilaterally and beyond.

The idea of revisiting the Gujral doctrine is not with an idealistic liberal perspective but with a rational motive of securing India's geopolitical interests by assuming leadership in regional confidence building which is sure to have its own cost. Further, in the neighborhood, it is highly unlikely that a tough posturing will help India exercise influence. It is also important to note that, Leadership flows from assuming responsibility, bearing patience and in capacity building to offer a good bargain.

Public Diplomacy: A Strategic Construction of Soft Power

The 'India Out' campaign has spread from Maldives to Bangladesh, and a similar sentiment prevails in differing proportions across South Asia (Wadud, 2023). This is by far the biggest challenge for India's Foreign Policy whether or not the state publicly acknowledges it. While some foreign policy analyst accuse India of having a "big brother" attitude in the region, there are others who point to these countries in the neighborhood of acting under influence of the "small state syndrome" (Bhattarai & Bista, 2024; Sharma, 2020). In either case the fact that there is a rise of anti-India sentiment, that there is a dominant big brotherly image of India among the people of SAARC countries is a challenge for India's Foreign Policy (Shivamurthy, 2022). Therefore, efforts need to be made to address this challenge, and the efforts should acknowledge the dynamics beyond the China factor. At this level, India's engagement with its neighborhood should be independent of the China policy. At the policy making table New Delhi should acknowledge the gaps in its own neighborhood policy instead of clubbing it with the Beijing threat (Moorthy, 2018).

The issue needs to be primarily dealt at two levels: firstly, there is a need for rebranding India's image in the neighborhood to the level of the masses through direct communication using different media platforms and exchange programs. Secondly, beyond the PR exercise, the rebranding initiatives should be backed by resources and intense engagement.

Further, there are some important considerations in

1. These activities need to be initiated at the non-governmental level with an effort of building trust by employing multiple actors to engage and increase people-to-people contact ("Asian Century Institute – India and the SAARC," n.d.) Entertainment industry, academia and inter-regional trading through small businesses have a key role to play. Organizing literary and art festivals, academic conferences, conducting projects similar to Hunar Haat and trade fairs, and engaging with experts on the issues concerning humanity like climate change can go a long way in building India's influence in the region (Rao & Rao, 2010).

2. The approach adopted in the process needs to be flexible, less confrontational and reactionary, and consistent even at the face of setbacks and without any intent of immediate reciprocity or credit. For example: Maldives was a case of strategic crisis which called for a more nuanced approach instead of being made a subject of full-blown social media war, further leading to inflated reactionary statements by senior officials on both sides (Bhushan, 2024; Ellis-Petersen, 2024).
3. In the case of India's Public Diplomacy, the primary motive is to win the good will of the people of the SAARC countries and influence the larger public opinion. The aim is to emphatically convey that India's public diplomacy is desired at building mutual trust, interdependence and collective growth to further achieve global peace and security, and is not a means of propaganda, or a pre-emptive move to counter China (Ramabadran, 2023). And, since, public diplomacy is about influencing governments through their public, it will also help make bilateral engagements less susceptible to change in governments in the neighborhood.
4. Further, at the state-to-state level, India's engagement should be independent of the party and nature of government in power. Our primary determinant should be protecting India's interest in security, economy and geo-politics. A case in point here is the celebration at the Dhaka university of India's defeat in the World Cup final, or the general anti-India sentiment that has resurfaced following a controversial election in Bangladesh. While these rhetorical stands may stem from the opposition Bangladesh Nationalist Party (BNP), it does find some ground among the people (Mahmud, 2024; Wadud, 2023). Therefore, whether Maldives, Bangladesh or Afghanistan, governments may come and go, India's efforts should be in strengthening its ties with the people of the SAARC countries. In the case with Afghanistan, while India had heavily invested in the infrastructural projects, the change in government has left the prospects of those investments without any light for the future (Majumdar, 2021).

5. Also, India should not allow the enhancement of its military might in the region to overwhelm its soft-power engagement. Its military expansion needs to be gradual, calculated and silent.

In the light of the geo-political developments in its neighborhood, it is important to note that India does not have a strategic soft power policy. In the Global Soft Power Index, 2024 published by Brand Finance, while United States takes the first position, China has overtaken United Kingdoms to assume the third spot, and India has slipped from the 28th to the 29th position (Fingar, 2024; "Global Soft Power Index: India's Ranking Slips From 28th to 29th Position," 2024). China spends an average of \$ 10 billion annually on soft power initiatives, while this figure is missing for India (Albert, 2018). Further, what is also a case of critical evaluation is the lack of efforts by India to build on its individual soft power initiatives which has been evident in the case with Nepal or Sri Lanka (Adhikari, 2018; Unal, 2021).

Strategic Revitalization of SAARC

According to the International Chamber of Commerce Bangladesh (ICCB), "South Asia is one of the least integrated regions in the world in terms of trade and people-to-people contact". The inter-regional trade in South Asia is less than 5%, while these figures are 50% for East Asia, 26% for ASEAN, 67% for EU, 62% for NAFTA, and 22% for LAC and COMESA. In terms of value the trade in the region is estimated to be \$ 23 billion well below its potential of \$ 67 billion (Report, 2023). SAARC accounts for 23% of the World Population, 15% of the World's arable land, but only 6% of the Purchasing Power Parity based Global GDP, and accounts for around 2% of world goods trade, and around 3% of global FDI, but more than 40% of the world's poor (Sandhu & Sidhu, 2014).

In view of this data, it becomes crucial to take constructive measure to revitalize the SAARC grouping.

1. Since mistrust is the primary cause of disruption, there is a need for a new platform [informal] within SAARC at least at the secretary level where there can be open dialogue, and measures can be taken for confidence building. This secretary level platform should be assisted by a common body of experts which works on mutually

understanding the information variable determining the states' strategies, that is to understand each other's foreign policy outlook in the larger global arena (Glaser, 2010).

2. People-to-people contact should be re-channelized and efforts need to be made to organize intra-regional academic, cultural, art and trade festivals. With Kartarpur Sahib corridor as an example (Kulkarni & Abbasi, 2018), an integrated network of similar corridors can be established in the region, strengthening the cultural diplomacy through people's religious engagement. A big achievement would be to establish the region as a mutual visa-free zone.
3. The SAARC Development Fund should be revitalized to address common concerns of climate change, agriculture, energy security, poverty alleviation and economic development.
4. Efforts need to be made to optimize on the region's trade potential by removing the trade barriers and implementing the already signed South Asian Free Trade Agreement (SAFTA), in light of the gravity model of trade. After all there are greater interests in purchasing goods from a kirana store next door, than to travel far off to buy it from a super-market.
5. And, as the above three measures begin to materialize, efforts can be made for greater connectivity and integration of the region realizing the vision of a South Asian Economic Union (SAEU) and moving towards self-reliance.

A well-integrated operational SAARC will ensure not only collective growth, but also be a formidable force in a realigning geo-politics. Strong regional foot hold will also allow India a leverage in its global ventures.

Discussions and Policy Recommendations

Since its very inception SAARC has been a very vulnerable organization. In fact, initially, in India, it was viewed as an attempt by the 'Lilliputs to get the Gulliver down' (Sandhu & Sidhu, 2014). While the animosity between India and Pakistan following the Uri attack was only incidental in making SAARC dis-functional, the discontentment had been building

up for long (Bhattacharjee, 2023). Therefore, for regional success SAARC needs to be re-oriented with clearer and specific objectives upon which there can be further construction in a phased and planned manner. With regards to Pakistan beyond the Terrorism – Kashmir interplay is the issue of mutual distrust in view of which India has over the last few years attempted to prevent the mainstreaming of Pakistan in geopolitics (Hussain, 2023). However, considering that both China and Pakistan are an irritant to India in the region, it is important to understand that in the non-revival of SAARC Pakistan has less to lose and China has more to gain. And, in the light of realpolitik China not Pakistan is competing with India in regional dominance and Global influence. Moreover, the recent political and economic history of Pakistan has reduced it to an administrative security state (Pattanaik, 2001). Given the situation, India needs to leverage on its relation with Pakistan, also given the fact that Pakistan will continue to be India's neighbor and a South Asian country. While its geo-political relevance has seen a significant down slide, the potential of its geo-strategic relevance will always remain (Hussain, 2023). Further, while it is critical to see SAARC through the China, Pakistan, and the larger geo-political prism, India should engage with the member countries more independently and constructively for regional growth and integration (Sharma, 2020).

There are some other important elements of Foreign Policy that India needs to consider for global engagement in general and for SAARC in particular:

1. Foreign Policies should be crafted to address both short-term and long-term objectives, with a visionary approach and strategic consideration. It should not be reactionary and the substance should be louder than the optics.
2. While Public diplomacy should be loud, strategic diplomacy should be silent and secret.
3. Domestic Policy should not overwhelm Foreign Policy.
4. Given the nature of contemporary geo-politics, Foreign Policy cannot be made in isolation.

Conclusion

In his letter to Edwina Mountbatten in 1950, C. Rajagopalachari, the last governor-general of India, wrote, “A country without material, men or money – the three means of power – is now fast coming to be recognized as the biggest moral power in the civilized world...her word listened to with respect in the councils of the great” (Guha, 2017). India has always been a reservoir of moral influence (Sharma, 2020), and now that it intensively expands its strategic influence to make geopolitical gains it should not lose the quotient of having the moral high ground in its foreign policy which is based on its cultural values. Whether big brother or not, India is a big power in the region, and a rising power in the world. As it advocates for the democratization of the global order and for multipolarity, its projection of being a growth engine of the world should begin by assuming the leadership of integrating the cause of people’s welfare in the home region. Being the bigger state, such a leadership role and initiation can be taken up only by India in the region. While national security continues to be of primary importance to India, the fourth powerful military in the world and the fifth largest economy should look at regional multilateralism from beyond the security dilemma with a broader geo-strategic and geo-economic view. India’s regional re-configuration will have an impact not only on its global ambitions, but also on the realignment process of the global geo-politics. New Delhi’s success in dealing the with multilayered diplomatic challenge in the neighborhood (Sofuoglu, 2021), will be a short in the arm for its global reputation.

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